

Determination of Material Models for Sandwich Panels with PIR Rigid Foam Experimental Investigations

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ABSTRACT

Sandwich panels, which are used in the construction industry as roof or façade cladding, are primarily assessed through tests. A deep understanding of the material parameters and the behaviour of sandwich panels is important for the design of these construction components. Due to the constant changes in the polyurethane (PU) foams used as a core material and the wide influence of several boundary conditions, the experimental database for the currently used foams is small. This article presents the findings of compression and tensile tests on sandwich panels with a core of polyisocyanurate (PIR) rigid foam (density: 41 kg/m³). The tests were performed in several spatial directions and over the range required by the standard EN 14509. The results of the tests showed the orthotropy of the core material and the dependence of the material on the direction and type of load. Using the data from this experimental study, a material model is presented, which was implemented in a numerical study. The model is separated in two parts and utilizes the Hill yield criterion to represent the orthotropy and non-linear part of the core material.

Keywords: sandwich panels, PIR-rigid foam, orthotropic material, Hill plasticity

1 INTRODUCTION

In the construction industry, sandwich panels are mainly used as roof and façade components (see *Fig. 1*). Due to the good strength-to-weight ratio and the short construction time, these panels are particularly popular and widely used in industrial and hall constructions. In this area of application, sandwich panels consist of two thin steel faces with a thicker core in between. The core material can be polyurethane (PU) rigid foam, or mineral wool (1). The PU rigid foam type currently used in sandwich panels is primarily polyisocyanurate (PIR) rigid foam. In the following, the initials PU include both the current PIR foam system and the foams known in the past as PUR (polyurethane).

Fig. 1. a) Industry building with sandwich panels; b) Roof sandwich panel with PU rigid foam and the defined spatial directions

The first industrial production of sandwich panels for construction took place in the 1960s (2). Since then, many studies have been carried out on laminate structures in general and some research has been carried out on sandwich structures as used in construction. In the basic literature e.g. (3), sandwich theories for calculation are presented. Here, it is assumed that the PU core behaves in a

linear-elastic, homogeneous, and isotropic way. In addition to this basic literature, there is a smaller amount of research that deals with a more detailed consideration of the stress-strain relationships in sandwich panels with PU-rigid foam for the construction industry.

Some research (e.g. (4; 5)) deals with mathematical approaches for the correlation between the isotropic cellular structure and the mechanical properties. Others (e.g. (6; 7)) contribute to the calculation of the wrinkling stress of inhomogeneous or anisotropic sandwich panels. During wrinkling, the compressed face sheet, which is supported by the core, fails in terms of stability. As a result, the face sheet wrinkles. The wrinkling failure of the compressed face sheet is declared as the usually decisive and design-relevant failure mode. However, the calculation in the responsible standard, EN 14509 (8), for this failure is based on the assumption of homogeneous and isotropic core layer.

Numerical investigations have been carried out in parallel in several areas. The most recent investigations are, for example, by Pozorski and Porzorska (9; 10). In their publications, they described different ways of implementing the PU rigid foam core.

Experimental investigations on sandwich panels with steel facings and a PUR rigid core were presented by different authors (e.g. (11; 12)). The focus of this research was on the wrinkling failure mode of the compressed face sheets. More experimental data are available on sandwich panels with different core and face materials(13-15). Due to the high variability of the material properties, the standard for sandwich panels in construction, EN 14509, provides the basis for test-based approvals. The literature listed here shows that there is a large number of analytical approaches for the more accurate design of sandwich panels. However, the focus of most research work is on the wrinkling failure mode. Failure of the core material is usually only dealt with to a minor extent. Furthermore, due to the constant and ongoing development of the core material, in particular the development from PUR to PIR in the last 10 years, previous experimental data sets cannot be directly transferred to the currently produced sandwich panels (16).

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The properties of sandwich panels, especially those of the core material, vary depending on the production process (foam mixture, temperature and geometry) and the environmental conditions (16–18). The production of sandwich panels is a continuous production line on a double-belt system. The outer and inner face sheets are unwound from coils and profiled. The PU foam is injected between the heated face sheets, which move at a speed of 6 to 8 m per minute. The exothermic reaction of polyol with isocyanates, and various additives, during the production process results in the formation of closed cells in which blowing agents in the form of pentane are trapped (19). *Fig 2 a)* describes the properties of the sandwich panels tested.

manufacturer M	
type	roof panel
core material	
material	PIR rigid foam
thickness ¹	100 mm
density ¹	40,85 kg/m ³

¹Mean value out of 216 measurements

a)

b)

Fig. 2. a) Properties of the tested sandwich panels; b) Simplified schematic representation of a cell element in form of a pentagon-dodecahedron with thick cell bars and thin cell walls. Based on (19).

Microscope images of the foam show that the largest proportion of the PU solid is located in the cell bars and cell nodes (20). The very thin cell walls are located between the cell bars and do not contribute to the load transfer. The cell bars are mainly responsible for load transfer (4). Due to the

continuous production, the cells, in the form of a pentagonal dodecahedron, were slightly longer in the production-direction of the panel than in the other spatial directions (*Fig. 2 b, 5a*) (20).

Tests based on the EN 14509:2013 standard (8) were carried out on the test specimens to determine the material parameters and behavior. To obtain more precise information, the tests were carried out beyond the requirements of the standard.

To determine the compression parameters square test specimens with a side length of 100 mm were used. The tests presented in this paper were carried out at a speed of 10%. The compression modulus of the core material (E_{Cc}) was determined via the slope in the linear elastic range. According to the standard, only the compression test in the direction of the element height (z-direction) and up to a strain of 10% is intended. The test set up is shown in *Fig. 3 a*.

Fig. 3. a) Compression tests set up; b) Tensile test set up

To determine the tensile parameters, cross-panel tests were carried out on cubes (100 mm). To ensure a uniform load application, plates were glued to the samples, and the load was applied on both sides of these plates (*Fig. 3b*). The tests were run until failure at a speed of 3% of the specimen height per minute. The tensile modulus (E_{Ct}) was determined using the gradient in the linear range between 20% and 40% of the maximum load (8).

As biaxial stress states also occur in the core material of sandwich panels, and the aim was to describe them as close to reality as possible, the compression and tensile tests were carried out in all three spatial directions: along the longitudinal axis of the panel (x), over the width of the panel (y), and over the thickness of the panel (z) (*Fig. 1b*).

3 RESULTS

The results described below show extracts from a series of tests on samples with a total of 240 individual tests. However, as described in beginning, the results for the material parameters are subject to a large scatter and are dependent on the manufacturer and the production process. A direct transfer of individual results shown by any sandwich panels should therefore only be carried out with caution. Nevertheless, further studies by the authors with sandwich samples from other manufacturers show the same tendencies in the results (21).

The results of the tests in different spatial directions are of particular importance. There is hardly any current experimental data in this field, and the results presented below represent an important milestone of detailed research into sandwich panels for the construction industry.

3.1 Compression Tests

Fig. 4 shows a stress-strain diagram of compression tests in the x-, y- and z-direction (for definition see *Fig. 1b*), up to a strain of almost 90% and the enlarged initial range. In general, there were three sections within each curve. In the initial range, an almost linear distribution appears. Subsequently, a plateau with approximately constant stress is formed with increasing deformation. From a strain of approximately 60%, a strong increase in stress appears with a slight increase in strain. This area is referred to as densification.

Considering the tests, which were loaded in the z-direction, a typical stress-strain curve for elastomeric foams with a characteristic hyper-elastic behavior can be seen (5). The tests were carried out up to the densification area without any recognizable foam fractures. With the unloading curves, the test specimens almost return to their original dimensions. The curves of the samples loaded in the x-direction behave like an elastic-plastic foam (5). The x-direction is significantly stiffer and brittle. After a short linear increase, it reaches a maximum at about 3%. After this, the stress initially drops to a plateau. In this direction even small compressions causes cracks in the foam and it was not possible to run all tests until the densification area. The stress-strain curves of the loads in the y-direction are arranged between those of the load directions x and z. Even if a slight maximum is recognizable at about 6%, the stress then does not drop as much as in the x-direction and no visible foam cracks appear. Therefore, the behavior in the y-direction can also be described as hyper-elastic. A high proportion of elastic deformation can be observed in all directions.

Fig. 4. a) Stress-strain diagram of compression tests in three spatial directions on 12 samples in each direction; b) enlarged initial range

The strong difference in the behaviour of the various directions in the tests can be explained by the pronounced orthotropy of the core material (Fig. 2 b, 5a). During the load increase, the cell bars initially begin to bent, which was characterized by the linear increase in deformation (Fig. 5b). In the predominantly plateauing area, with its characterized low gradient, the cell bars buckled (Fig. 5c). Occasionally, the thin cell walls may tear open. When the bulging gets severe, so that the opposing cell bars abut and touch each other, the densification begins and the stress increases (22). The stress-strain curve then behaves analogously to that of the solid material of the cells (23) and the cell walls rupture completely. However, the blowing agent pentane escaped from the sample when the pressure was released. This was recognized by the smell that emerged from the sample at this point.

Due to the elongated shape of the cells, there was more solid material (cell bars) in the x-direction. As a result, the stiffness due to the bending of the cell bars was significantly greater than in the y- and z-direction. However, when loaded in the x-direction, the cell bars aligned in the direction of force were also significantly longer and were subjected to greater compression. The bending of the cell walls was followed by a stability failure of the cell bars in the x-direction. However, plastic hinges formed at the nodes of the cell walls before this. If these plastic hinges formed at several cells along the cross-section, the visually recognizable cracks could be observed. Foam fractures occurred at the edges of the specimen. The escape of the blowing agent could already be detected during the tests, as the cells opened due to the bursting of the cell walls when compression was applied in the x-direction and recognizable foam fractures occurred.

Fig. 5. Simplified schematic representation of a) cell geometry and orientation in the unloaded state; b) bending of the cell bars in the linear-elastic range c) non-linear deformation of the cells under compression load with a large deformation at almost constant load occurs due to buckling of the cell bars and walls. Based on (24).

The 5% fractile value is calculated in addition to the mean value and the standard deviation. Fig. 6 shows the mean values of 12 tests each as well as their corresponding standard deviation and the 5% fractile value.

For the comparison of compressive parameters presented here, the maximum value within 10% strain was compared. The stiffness was determined in the range from 20% to 40% of this maximum value. As shown in Fig. 4, the maximum is at 10% strain for the tests in the z-direction, while the tests in the x-direction reach the maximum in this range at around 3% strain. In the y-direction, the maximum value is generally about 6% strain.

The greatest strength and stiffness are shown in the x-direction. The lowest material values are achieved in the component thickness direction. Here, the strength is reduced by 60% and the stiffness by 82% compared to the x-direction. However, it should be noted that the y- and z-directions can achieve even higher stress without visible foam fractures due to their hyper-elastic behaviour with greater elongation. In the x-direction, the first visible defects appear in the foam when the maximum value is reached.

Fig. 6. Distribution along the load direction with standard deviation and 5% fractile value with a sample scope of 12 tests. a) compression strength b) strain at the maximum stress within 10% strain c) compression stiffness.

3.2 Tensile Tests

Fig. 7 shows the stress-strain distribution from tensile tests along the x-, y- and z-direction according to the standard. The graphs are almost linear-elastic up to failure and thus exhibited a different material behavior than under compression. The foam behaved in a brittle way and the failure was typically a foam fracture. Also typical for the investigated foam systems was the higher compressive strength within 10% compression compared to the tensile strength at failure.

Compared to the compression tests, the tensile tests generally show a higher scattering at the maximum strength. This is due to the sensitivity of the tensile tests to blow holes (defects in the foam)

and the inhomogeneity of the foam across the width and height of the panel. Compared to the tensile strength, the stiffness did not scatter significantly. The red lines in Fig. 7 represent average curves of each load direction.

Fig. 7. Stress-strain diagram of tensile tests in three spatial directions on 10 to 12 samples in each direction. The red lines represent average curves.

However, differences could be seen in the mean values of the tensile stiffness and strength as well as in the elongation at failure. These results are consistent with the findings from the compression tests. The greatest stiffness and strength were obtained in the x-direction. The load was introduced into the long and numerous cell bars which were predominantly aligned parallel to this direction. The elongation was low because the long cell bars were mainly loaded in tension and the neighboring short cell bars only experienced little bending before they finally failed. The bending of the cell bars near the cell nodes was mainly responsible for the linear deformation. In the tests shown here, it is noticeable that the stiffness in the thickness direction (z-direction) was on average 78% lower than in the transverse x-direction. The strength was also on average 53% below the tensile strength in the y-direction. The higher elongation compared to the x-direction was due to the stronger branching of the cells along the two other load directions. This results in increased bending of the cell bars.

Fig. 8. Distribution along the load direction with standard deviation and 5% fractile value with a sample scope of 12 tests. a) tensile strength b) strain at fracture c) tensile stiffness.

4 NUMERICAL INVESTIGATIONS AND DISCUSSION

The numerical analysis was carried out with Ansys 2022 R2 Workbench. Particular attention was paid to the implementation of the material model of the closed-cell PU rigid foam core. Based on various preliminary investigations (21) the PU rigid foam was defined with two different parts: first the linear elastic range using orthotropic elasticity and second the non-linear part, which appeared in

the compression tests and was implemented using the Hill yield criterion. The Hill yield criterion is a way of determining yield stress levels in different spatial directions and planes and is a suitable criterion for describing anisotropic plastic deformations (25).

This model does not differentiate between the loads “tension” and “compression”. The hardening in the form of stress-strain relationships cannot be defined separately for the individual directions and planes. Only the point of yielding can be adjusted for every direction. Due to the lower tensile strength compared to the compressive strength at the yield point, the material model is also used to visualize the tensile tests. In (21) more precise information are given.

Fig. 9 shows the correlation between the numerical and experimental data. The dominant loading direction is the z-direction, thus this direction was used to calibrate the non-linear part. At higher strains, the numerical model cannot be used. A hyper-elastic material model can be applied to represent those strains.

The tensile data do not fit as well as the compression data because the material model was calibrated with the compression tests. Taking the large scatter into account, which can be observed in the tensile trial data (see Fig. 7), the numerical model (black curves) was within an acceptable range for sandwich panels used in construction. The red curves in Fig. 9 b represent the average curves of each direction. The green curves visualize some trial data from the experimental investigations.

Fig. 9. Comparison of the trial data and the numerical data a) of the compression tests; b) of the tensile tests.

The various types of material behaviour and the resulting maximum loads are of great interest to the construction industry. Of relevance is the wrinkling of the steel faces and the core fractures. Wrinkling occurs mainly in the bending capacity tests when the specimen is primarily subjected to bending. This bending generates normal stresses in the face sheet, which lead to a stability failure of the face that is under compression and supported by the core. Analytically, the maximum wrinkling stress is determined via the material parameters of the core (E_C , G_C), which result from the small-scale tests, and the stiffness of the face sheets (E_F). For this purpose, an E-modulus of the foam is determined by average the compressive and tensile stiffness (3). As you can see in the results ahead, the stiffness of compression and tension are in a similar range, but there are still differences which lead to the deviation shown in Fig. 9. For a uniform deviation of the numerical results from the experimental test data, the linear-elastic initial range can be calibrated not only on the compression tests, but also by averaging the linear-elastic ranges of the compression and tensile tests.

The core failure of the PIR rigid foam occurs when the maximum stress in tension, shear, compression, or multiaxial constellation exceeds the resistance. This failure can be determined in the numerical calculations via the stress tensors of the core and their state with the use of the Tsai–Wu failure criterion (13). Compared to the Tsai–Wu failure criterion, the often classically used von Mises

failure criterion is limited to primarily isotropic materials and is only a rough approximation for highly anisotropic materials. The shear stresses are taken into account in the von Mises criterion via the equivalent stresses. In contrast, the shear stresses in the Tsai–Wu criterion are considered in a more complex way via the specific material parameters for the shear stress. However, the more specific Tsai–Wu failure criterion can be converted into the von Mises failure criterion in certain cases. The Tsai–Wu failure criterion can be used to describe the stress failure for anisotropic materials e.g. the core. This failure criterion is characterized by the consideration of structural anisotropy and a distinction between compressive and tensile strengths (27).

Based on the sandwich load-bearing effect in which the core material receives pure constant shear stresses, and the normal stresses are transferred via the face sheets, the failure appears to be caused by a core fracture when the maximum shear strength is reached. However, normal stresses also occur in the core material due to concentrated load application and indentations at supports. The core is then biaxially loaded, and the failure can be described in this area using the Tsai–Wu criterion. Hassinen 1999 (28) already mentioned investigations of two-span sandwich panels in which it was found that the von Mises criterion does not apply to PU rigid foams. Hassinen showed that PU actually has higher capacities with the simultaneous effect of shear and compression than the von Mises criterion estimates.

5 CONCLUSION

This article describes the material behavior of sandwich panels, consisting of steel faces and a PU rigid foam (41 kg/m^3) core, in the construction industry under compression and tension loads in different spatial direction. The most important results are listed below:

- *The tests showed a strong directional dependence of the foam system. The orthotropy was caused in particular by different cell geometries in the different spatial directions.*
- *The tests specified in the standard (EN 14509) are not sufficient for a detailed description of the core material.*
- *In compression tests an almost hyper-elastic material was found in y- and z-direction. The foam can be compressed in these directions by up to 90% without any cracks. In the x-direction, the core material behaved more like an elastic-plastic foam material. Cracks in the foam occurred even with small compression. The maximum strength and stiffness were detected in the production direction. In z-direction there is a reduction of the material parameters of almost 80%.*
- *Under tensile stress, PIR failed as a brittle material. The maximum strength and stiffness appeared in the production direction. The tensile strength was generally lower than the compression strength. The values in panel thickness direction are around 78% (stiffness) and 53% (strength) less than in production direction.*
- *In the numerical model presented in this paper, an orthotropic elasticity with plastic hardening according to the Hill yield criterion was used to represent the PIR rigid foam.*
- *The analysis suggest that the classical failure criterion according to von Mises is not valid for the PIR foam used in the investigated sandwich panels. The Tsai–Wu failure criterion is proposed here.*

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